

A Study on Shareholders Wealth (value) Creation with Special Reference to Banking Companies

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Abstract

The Indian corporates have matured, leaving behind those days where investors were just a source of funds. The investors expect higher value for their investment. There are some existing models accepted and employed all over the world to measure the share holder's wealth creation. One of such model is EVA. It is the popular idea for measuring shareholder's value. Now a day the demand for shareholders value is rising more strongly than ever. However, the measuring parameters like Return on Investment (ROI) and Earnings per Share (EPS) have failed to consider the most important aspect (i.e.) called shareholders wealth creation (value creation). In this study, an attempt is made to empirically analyse how the EVA helps to measure the shareholders wealth (value) creation. From the study it can be clearly understood that EVA gives the better share holder's value rather than the ROCE and Market Capitalisation.

Keywords: Economic Value added, Shshare holders' wealth creation, Return on Investment, Earning per shares, value creation

Economic Value Added (EVA) and shareholders wealth (value) Creation - An Empirical Analysis

Introduction

In recent years, the main objectives of corporate have shifted to the creation of value and achieving satisfactory returns via increasing profitability and shareholders wealth. Among other stakeholders, the creation of value to shareholders is an important key to success in a developed business environment. In general, it is accepted that the value is created when the firm generates or sustains returns that are more than its cost of capital. There are hence many indicators that can be used to measure share holders wealth creation including Economic Value Added and Market Value Added. The excess returns generated by a company are higher than the cost of capital is called as value. Creating value for shareholders is the widely accepted concept. Gone are those days where the investors are considered only as a source of

investment. There are various models used to measure the shareholders value creation both in India and in other countries. These include Cash Flow Returns on Investment (CFROI) by the Boston consultancy group, Cash Value Added (CVA) and Shareholders Value Added (SVA). Besides all these, there is the concept of Economic Value Added (EVA), which is most popular.

Measurement of Shareholder's Wealth

The following methods are used for measures the shareholder's wealth creation in India.

1. **Return on Capital Employed (ROCE):** Return on Capital Employed is the post tax version of earning power. It is a ratio that indicates the efficiency and profitability of a company's capital investments.
2. **Market Capitalisation:** Market Capitalisation is a measure of a company's total value. It is estimated by determining the cost of buying an entire business in its current state and often referred to as "market cap".
3. **Market Value Added (MVA):** Market Value added shows the difference between the market value of a company and the capital contributed by investors (both bondholders and shareholders). In other words, it is the sum of all capital claims held against the company plus the market value of debt and equity.
4. **Economic Value Added (EVA):** EVA means excess of profit, which remains after deducting the company's cost of capital (viz debt and equity). It is nothing but a measure of the values a commercial enterprise has created for its shareholders.

Review of Literature

To study share holders wealth creation using Economic value added, Market value added Return on capital employed and Market capitalization the following relevant studies from India and abroad are reviewed.

Economic Value Added (EVA) and Shareholders Wealth Creation: A Factor Analytic Approach BY **A.Vijayakumar (2011)** examine whether EVA has got a better predictive power of selected automobile companies in India or not. Finally the author found that out of the eight variables, three factors have been extracted and these three factors put together explain 69.902 per cent of the total variance. Further, sales and profit after tax are found to have a stronger relationship with EVA.

Perways Alam and shaik Mohammed Nixzamuiddin (2012) in their study entitled "Performance Measures of Shareholders Wealth: An Application of Economic Value Added (EVA)" emphasized that Economic Value Added (EVA) is a value based performance measure that gives importance on value creation by the management for the owners. Profit maximization as a concept is age-old, wealth maximization is matured and value maximization is today's wisdom. Stern Stewart's EVA raises storm in corporate world and gives a new way to think about rewarding management.

Avijit Sikdar (2013) in his research paper entitled "Value based performance indicators versus accounting earnings based performance indicators- A case study with reference to ONGC" attempted to examine the relationship between share price and market value added, economic value added and cash value added. Finally the author concluded that all the traditional earning based measure except EPS fails to capture the share price variation strongly and value-based measures like EVA, CVA and MVA have emerged as the effective performance measures.

A study by **Madan Lal Bhasin (2013)** entitled "Economic Value Added and Shareholders' Wealth Creation: Evidence from a Developing Country" state that Economic Value Added (EVA) framework is gradually replacing the traditional measures of financial performance on account of its robustness. Finally the researcher concluded that "there is no strong evidence to support Stern Stewart's claim that EVA is superior to the traditional performance measures in its association with MVA."

Economic value added and shareholders' wealth creation: the portrait of a developing Asian country by **Junaid M. Shaikh (2013)** examines the value-creation strategies of selected Indian companies by analysing whether EVA better represents the market-value of these companies in comparison to conventional performance measures. The study indicates that "there is no strong evidence to support Stern Stewart's claim that EVA is superior to the traditional performance measures in its association with MVA".

Shrikant Krupasindhu Panigrahi (2017) studied the "Economic Value Added and Traditional Accounting Measures for Shareholder's Wealth Creation" investigated performance measurement tools and shareholder's wealth relationships in the context of Malaysian public listed construction companies. The results conclusively support that market value added (MVA) is found to have a negative relationship with created shareholder value (CSV) contradicting with the theory that confirmed, the increase in shareholder value when there is an increase in stock market value and efficiency.

A study entitled "Creating a new valuation tool for South African agricultural cooperatives" by **M Geyser & IE Liebenberg (2013)** examines introducing Economic Value Added (EVA) as a performance measure for agribusinesses and co-ops in South Africa. Finally the authors concluded that EVA is an effective measure of the quality of managerial decisions as well as a reliable indicator of an enterprise's value growth in future.

Sliman S. Alsoboa (2017), "The Influence of Economic Value Added and Return on Assets on Created Shareholders Value: A Comparative Study in Jordanian Public Industrial Firms" address the relationship between Economic Value Added (EVA) and Created Shareholders Value (CSV) in Jordanian public industrial firms (JPIF), the result shows that superiority of EVA in predicting and evaluating the CSV could be put into a conclusive and positive light compared to ROA. One financial measure cannot be enough to measure neither CSV nor firms performance.

Creation of shareholder value: A comparison of economic value added (EVA) with traditional performance measures by **M. Shotter, C. Dennis, L. Briimmer and A. Boshoff (1998)**, Investigates the strength of association of Economic Value Added with Shareholder Value and compares this association to that of traditional performance measures. The researchers concluded that correlation between MVA and EVA as well as other indicators over a ten year period in respect of industrial companies listed on the Johannesburg Stock Exchange, and finds that the strongest correlation exists between MVA and EVA.

Statement of the problem

Most of the foreign countries have succeeded in implementing EVA at top level management. It improves their capital efficiency and overall performance. But in India there are many problems faced by industries regarding the structural weakness not only in the field of finance but also in other areas like, marketing, personnel, wealth of shareholders, employees and owners. In order to solve these problems many studies have undertaken with the help of various financial tools. But all these financial tools are not effectively evaluate the shareholders wealth using financial statement. EVA gives ways to overcome the structural weakness of the industry/company. Hence, an attempt is made in this study to measure the shareholders wealth (value) creation using economic value added concept in the field of banking industry.

Scope of the study

This study covers the four different components like Economic Value Added (EVA), Market Value Added (MVA), Return on Capital Employed (ROCE) and Market capitalization from five different banks like Axis Bank Ltd, Bank of Baroda, Bank of India, Canara Bank and HDFC

Bank. In this study an attempt is made to measure the value of shareholder by measuring two basic performances of the Company viz-internal (ie) cash divisions and external (ie) value by financial results.

Objectives of the study

The study is carried out with the following objectives.

1. To identify the various methods used to measure shareholders wealth creation.
2. To compare Economic Value Added (EVA) with Market Value Added (MVA), Return on Capital Employed (ROCE) and Market capitalization of the sample companies.

Methodology of Study

This study tries to examine the relationship Economic Value Added (EVA) with Market Value Added (MVA), Return on Capital Employed (ROCE) and Market capitalization for the period of 2016-17. The sample for the present study includes Axis Bank Ltd, Bank of Baroda, Bank of India, Canara Bank and HDFC Bank. For the purpose of the sample, present study used the top five banks from National Stock Exchange Nifty Bank Index. The data used in the present study were collected from National Stock Exchange, concern sample banks website, books and records of sample banks.

Tools used for analysis of the present study:

1. EVA

Eva is the function of net operating profit after tax, cost of capital and capital employed in the business.

$$\text{EVA} = (\text{NOPAT} - (\text{WACC} * \text{Net Cap}))$$

Where

NOPAT = Net Operating Profit After Tax

WACC = Weighted Average Cost of Capital

Net Cap = Net Economic Capital Employed

2. MVA

MVA is essentially the difference between a company's current market value as determined by its stock price and its economic book value.

$$\text{MVA} = \text{No. of equity shares outstanding} * \text{Market Price per Share.}$$

3. Return on capital employed:

The return on capital employed means the rate of return produced by the firm against investment made by it.

$$\text{ROCE} = \frac{\text{Profit Before Interest and Tax (1-Taxrate)}}{\text{Average Total Asset}}$$

4. Market Capitalisation

Total market value of the company shares is called as market Capitalisation.

$$\text{Market Capitalisation} = \text{No Shares issued} * \text{Market Price per Share}$$

Limitations of the Study

1. In the present study the Economic Value Added (EVA) is calculated by using the secondary data. In case any defects in the secondary data that will affect the accuracy of the result.
2. The present study uses only five banks like Axis Bank Ltd, Bank of Baroda, Bank of India, Canara Bank and HDFC Bank only. If the present study covers all the sample banks in the NSE Nifty Bank index means it will be complete one.

3. The present study attempted to study relationship Economic Value Added (EVA) with Market Value Added (MVA), Return on Capital Employed (ROCE) and Market capitalization for the period of 2016-17 only. Hence the scope of the study is limited.

Analysis of Study

The higher the Economic Value Added (EVA), the better. A high EVA indicates the company has created substantial wealth for the shareholders. MVA is equivalent to the present value of all future expected EVAs. Negative EVA means that the value of the actions and investments of management is less than the value of the capital contributed to the company by the capital markets. This means that wealth or value has been destroyed. From this study, it comes to know that all the sample companies obtained higher EVA, which indicates that all the companies have created value for the shareholders.

Table 1
Values of EVA, MVA, ROCE and Market Capitalisation of Axis Bank Ltd

S. No.	Particulars	Rs. In Millions
1	Economic Value Added (EVA)	4985.65
2	Market Value Added(MVA)	37967.49
3	Return on Capital Employed (ROCE)	24.19
4	Market Capitalisation	38544.57

Table 1 shows the Economic Value Added (EVA), Market Value Added (MVA), Return on Capital Employed (ROCE) and Market Capitalisation of Axis Bank Ltd. From this analysis it understand that the EVA of Axis Bank Ltd is 4985.65 Million, MVA is 37967.49, ROCE is 24.19 million and Market capitalization is 38544.57 respectively. It is understand from the above analysis that Axis Bank Ltd obtained higher EVA, it indicates that Axis Bank Ltd have created value for the shareholders.

Table 2
Values of EVA, MVA, ROCE and Market Capitalisation of Bank of Baroda

S. No.	Particulars	Rs. In Millions
1	Economic Value Added (EVA)	2167.22
2	Market Value Added(MVA)	72688.5
3	Return on Capital Employed (ROCE)	19.36
4	Market Capitalisation	73935.0

Table -2 depicts the Economic Value Added (EVA), Market Value Added (MVA), Return on Capital Employed (ROCE) and Market Capitalisation of Bank of Baroda. From the above analysis it comes to know that the EVA of Bank of Baroda is 2167.22 Million, MVA is 72688.5 Million, ROCE is 19.36 Million and Market capitalization is 73935.0 respectively. It is understand from the above analysis that Bank of Baroda obtained higher EVA, it indicates that Bank of Baroda have created value for the shareholders.

Table 3
Values of EVA, MVA, ROCE and Market Capitalisation of Bank of India

S. No.	Particulars	Rs. In Millions
1	Economic Value Added (EVA)	761.56
2	Market Value Added(MVA)	59732.15
3	Return on Capital Employed (ROCE)	41.96
4	Market Capitalisation	65730.96

Table -3 reveals the Economic Value Added (EVA), Market Value Added (MVA), Return on Capital Employed (ROCE) and Market Capitalisation of Bank of India. From the above analysis it is understand that the EVA of Bank of India is 761.56 Million, MVA is 59732.15 Million, ROCE is 41.96 Million and Market capitalization is 65730.96 respectively. It is understand from the above analysis that Bank of India obtained higher EVA, it indicates that Bank of India have created value for the shareholders.

Table 4
Values of EVA, MVA, ROCE and Market Capitalisation of Canara Bank

S. No.	Particulars	Rs. In Millions
1	Economic Value Added (EVA)	5184.537
2	Market Value Added(MVA)	34846.95
3	Return on Capital Employed (ROCE)	32.69
4	Market Capitalisation	35930.62

Table -4 shows the Economic Value Added (EVA), Market Value Added (MVA), Return on Capital Employed (ROCE) and Market Capitalisation of Canara Bank. From the above analysis it is understand that the EVA of Canara Bank is 5184.537Million, MVA is 34846.95Million, ROCE is 32.69Million and Market capitalization is 35930.62respectively. The above analysis reveals the fact that Canara Bank obtained higher EVA, it indicates that Canara Bank have created value for the shareholders.

Table 5
Values of EVA, MVA, ROCE and Market Capitalisation of HDFC Bank

S. No.	Particulars	Rs. In Millions
1	Economic Value Added (EVA)	3276.32
2	Market Value Added(MVA)	83689.4
3	Return on Capital Employed (ROCE)	21.47
4	Market Capitalisation	44746.01

Table -5 depicts the Economic Value Added (EVA), Market Value Added (MVA), Return on Capital Employed (ROCE) and Market Capitalisation of HDFC Bank. From the above analysis it is understand that the EVA of HDFC Bank is 3276.32 Million, MVA is 83689.4 Million, ROCE is 21.47Million and Market capitalization is 44746.01respectively. The above analysis reveals the fact that HDFC Bank obtained higher EVA, it indicates that HDFC Bank have created value for the shareholders.

Findings, Suggestions and Conclusion of the present study

a. Findings of the Study

1. From the study it can be clearly understood that an on average EVA gives the better share holder's value rather than the ROCE and Market Capitalisation for all sample banks.
2. The EVA is not over estimated or not under estimated like the Market Capitalisation and ROCE.
3. From the study it can be found that, when consider the Economic Value added (EVA) alone, Canara Bank has created more wealth to the shareholders.
4. From the above analysis it can be understand that, when consider the Market Value Added (MVA) alone, HDFC Bank shareholders enjoy the maximum wealth creation.
5. It understand from the study that, when consider the Return on Capital Employed (ROCE) alone the Bank of India shareholders gained more wealth creation.
6. While considering the market Capitalisation alone, Bank of India performed well then the other sample companies.
7. In overall performance Canara bank is considered as best company in creating the share holders wealth and capital contribution.

b. Suggestions

From the study it can be clearly understood that EVA gives the better share holder's value rather than the ROCE and Market Capitalisation. The EVA is not over estimated or not under estimated like the Market Capitalisation and ROCE. It is general argument that at the time of selling the shares, Market Capitalisation is considered as the realization value. But in reality market price involves high volatility with high risk. Hence there is no guarantee for shareholders to realize the value mentioned in the balance sheet. But at the time using EVA it gives considerable value as well as reduces the risk. In Indian scenario, EVA is not popularly accepted in measuring corporate performance because the corporate cannot believe that shareholder's wealth can be through subtracting Cost of Capital from income. If EVA is to be accepted as an effective metric of corporate performance, there are more to be done and one such area is better disclosure norms for the performance Indian companies.

Conclusion

It is general argument that at the time of selling the shares, Market Capitalisation is considered as the realization value. But in reality market price involves high volatility with high risk. EVA and MVA do not correlate perfectly because expected EVA measures the current performance of expected share prices reflection. Hence the companies which are adopting the EVA must keep the current share price without any down trend. MVA cannot be calculated for all companies especially closely held companies and non profit organization because they are not holding the publicly traded shares. Creating the shareholders value is the fundamental goal of every corporate. EVA as a new metric of measuring economic value created by the corporate houses in another mile stone in the field of finance.

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